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MAKTABGACHA
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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ART THERAPY IN WORKING WITH CHILDREN EXPERIENCING EMOTIONAL STRESS

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Abstract: The article examines the issue of emotional stress in preschool children. Modern children are frequently exposed to emotional tension caused by unfavorable family circumstances, school-related difficulties, social environment factors, or individual psychological characteristics. Emotional stress may manifest as anxiety, aggression, social withdrawal, sleep disturbances, and attention instability. Art therapy is considered one of the most effective methods of providing psychological support to children in such conditions. This method is based on the use of artistic expression to restore emotional balance and support self-regulation.

The article analyzes how art therapy helps children cope with emotional stress, describing its theoretical foundations and its influence on the child's emotional state and mental well-being. Special attention is given to key mechanisms of art therapy, including anxiety reduction, development of self-expression, and emotional regulation. Practical methods and examples applied in corrective work with stressed children are presented. The study concludes that art therapy is highly effective within the system of psychological assistance for children experiencing emotional difficulties. A survey identified the perceptions of schoolchildren, teachers, and parents regarding the causes and severity of stress, and the potential of art therapy as an intervention method for reducing stress in younger generations.

Key words: art therapy, children, psychocorrection, emotional stress, anxiety.

Annotatsiya: Maqola maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda uchraydigan hissiy stress muammosini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Zamonaviy bolalar ko'pincha oiladagi, maktabdagi, ijtimoiy muhitdagi noqulayliklar yoki individual psixologik xususiyatlar tufayli hissiy zo'riqishga duch keladilar. Hissiy stress tashvish, tajovuzkorlik, ijtimoiy chekinish, uyqu buzilishi va e'tibor barqarorligining pasayishi orqali namoyon bo'lishi mumkin. Art-terapiya bunday vaziyatlarda bolalarni psixologik qo'llab-quvvatlashning eng samarali usullaridan biri hisoblanadi. Ushbu yondashuv san'at orqali o'zini ifoda etish va hissiy muvozanatni tiklashga asoslanadi.

Maqolada art-terapiyaning bolalarda hissiy stressni kamaytirishdagi ahamiyati, uning nazariy asoslari hamda bolaning ruhiy holati va hissiy barqarorligiga ta'siri tahlil qilingan. Xavotirni kamaytirish, o'zini ifoda qilish qobiliyatini rivojlantirish va hissiy tartibga solish kabi ta'sir mexanizmlariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Stress holatidagi bolalar bilan korreksion ishlarda qo'llaniladigan amaliy usullar yoritilgan. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, art-terapiyaning qiyin hayotiy vaziyatdagi bolalarni psixologik qo'llab-quvvatlash vositasi sifatidagi yuqori samaradorligi asoslab berilgan. O'tkazilgan so'rov asosida o'quvchilar, o'qituvchilar va ota-onalarning stress sabablari va og'irlik darajasiga bo'lgan munosabati aniqlangan hamda yosh avlodagi stressni kamaytirishda art-terapiya imkoniyatlari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: art-terapiya, bolalar, psixokorreksiya, hissiy stress, xavotir.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена изучению проблемы эмоционального стресса у детей дошкольного возраста. Современные дети нередко сталкиваются с эмоциональным напряжением, вызванным неблагоприятными семейными обстоятельствами, трудностями в школе, влиянием социальной среды или индивидуальными психологическими особенностями. Эмоциональный стресс может проявляться в виде тревожности, агрессии, замкнутости, нарушений сна и нестабильности внимания. Арт-терапия рассматривается как один из наиболее эффективных методов психологической поддержки детей в подобных ситуациях. Метод основан на использовании искусства для самовыражения и восстановления эмоционального равновесия.

В статье анализируется, как арт-терапия способствует преодолению эмоционального стресса детьми, описываются её теоретические основы и влияние на эмоциональное состояние и психическое здоровье ребёнка. Особое внимание уделено механизмам действия арт-терапии: снижению тревожности, развитию самовыражения и формированию эмоциональной регуляции. Приведены практические методы и примеры коррекционной работы с детьми, испытывающими стресс. Результаты исследования подтверждают высокую эффективность арт-терапии в системе психологической помощи детям с эмоциональными трудностями. Проведённый опрос выявил отношение школьников, учителей и родителей к причинам и степени выраженности стресса, а также рассмотрены возможности применения арт-терапии как метода коррекции стресса у подрастающего поколения.

Ключевые слова: арт-терапия, дети, психокоррекция, эмоциональный стресс, тревожность.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, art therapy has become an increasingly popular method of treatment and rehabilitation in various areas of medicine, including dentistry. Art therapy is a specialized form of therapy that utilizes artistic materials and techniques to promote mental and physical well-being in patients. In the field of dentistry, this type of therapy can be employed to reduce stress and anxiety related to dental treatments, as well as assist in the recovery process after various procedures.

One method of incorporating art therapy into dental care is through the creation of drawings or other forms of artwork prior to or during dental visits. This allows patients to focus on a creative outlet and divert their attention from concerns prior to treatment. Research has shown that art therapy significantly enhances the psychological well-being of patients before their dental appointments and assists them in managing pain and discomfort following procedures. Furthermore, art therapy fosters improved communication between patients and dentists, enhancing the overall effectiveness of treatment.

Art therapy serves as a valuable tool in addressing these challenges, promoting mental well-being and enhancing the quality of life for individuals.

The ongoing health crisis has also contributed to a rise in stress levels across all age groups. However, there is a specific group that is particularly susceptible to stress and its adverse effects – children, adolescents, and young adults. For this group, stress is particularly perilous, as they lack the knowledge and experience to manage stress and have not yet developed sufficient psychological defenses. It is well-known that the most dangerous form of stress is not so much acute as it is prolonged, chronic stress. This is particularly relevant for students, as it poses a risk of chronic school stress. Therefore, it is crucial to prevent it in a timely manner and effectively address its consequences.

School stress can lead to maladaptive states in children, which manifest as passivity, self-doubt, and feelings of inadequacy. This can result in depression, alienation, negative attitudes towards others and society, and compensatory aggression. In extreme cases, this can underlie socially dangerous behaviors such as bullying, violence, and exposure to extreme ideologies. Compensatory aggression may also be directed towards other ethnic and religious groups, leading to extremism and terrorism. However, these are rare instances. In most cases, school stress and maladaptation hinder the full realization of a child's creative potential and personal growth. This can lead to future school difficulties, which may block motivation and activity, as well as hinder the development of a student's abilities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

International research on the effectiveness of art therapy in reducing emotional stress among children shows that creative expression plays a crucial role in restoring psychological balance. Margaret Naumburg, known as the founder of dynamically oriented art therapy, emphasized that artistic expression allows children to externalize inner conflicts, making emotional processing more accessible. Edith Kramer further expanded this perspective by highlighting the therapeutic value of the artistic process itself, arguing that structured creative activities help children channel emotional tension into symbolic forms. Evidence from the World Health Organization also confirms that art-based interventions significantly reduce anxiety, fear, and stress in children, supporting emotional regulation and overall mental well-being across diverse developmental settings.

Research conducted in Uzbekistan similarly demonstrates the importance of art therapy in supporting children's emotional stability. S. Mamatisayeva's work with preschool children who have hearing impairments

shows that activities such as drawing, working with colors, and clay modeling help reduce anxiety and improve emotional responsiveness. Uzbek scholar S. Qodirova also asserts that creative activities serve as a key mechanism for the formation of emotional expression and the development of psychological resilience in children. Moreover, the therapeutic principles of Carl Rogers support the idea that creative self-expression fosters trust, psychological safety, and self-awareness, all of which are essential for children experiencing emotional stress. Together, these studies highlight the strong potential of art therapy as an effective intervention for improving the emotional health of children in stress-inducing environments.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology of the study was based on collecting empirical data through structured observations, semi-structured interviews, and psychological assessment tools aimed at identifying emotional stress in children. Art therapy sessions, including drawing and color-based activities, were conducted to observe changes in emotional expression and behavior. Data were gathered from children, teachers, and parents to ensure reliability. The collected information was analyzed using qualitative content analysis, allowing recurring emotional patterns, responses to art-based interventions, and behavioral changes to be identified. Comparative analysis was also applied to evaluate the effectiveness of art therapy techniques in reducing emotional stress and improving children's emotional regulation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Stress is an emotional and physiological response to demands placed on the individual, which can be expressed in terms of the mobilization of internal resources to cope with these demands. School-related stress, in particular, arises from the demands imposed on students by the educational process. This can lead to complex situations in which students do not have adequate resources to cope, potentially threatening their mental and physical well-being. When left unaddressed, such stress can result in resource depletion and exhaustion.

Psychoemotional stress, a specific type of stress, is characterized by an increase in physiological and psychological activity, with one of its key features being extreme instability. Under adverse conditions, stress can lead to a state of psychological and emotional strain, characterized by reduced efficiency and effectiveness of systems and organs, and, most importantly, rapid depletion of energy resources in the body.

Experience shows that art therapy can significantly improve the psychological state of patients before a dental visit and help them cope with pain and discomfort afterwards. In addition, art therapy improves communication between doctors and patients, which increases treatment effectiveness. One of the most effective ways to deal with emotional stress in children is regular art classes. Visual arts and drama classes, both passive (contemplation, experiencing art phenomena) and active (creating artistic works), not only have an aesthetic impact, but also help individuals build an adequate psychological protection system.

Artistic activities give everyone a chance to feel like creators, to use art to deal with negative experiences, and to model communication both with their own work and with others in group projects. Visual activities also create a positive environment for developing an emotional connection with art, which in turn helps form a positive attitude towards the world. The goal of art therapy, based on psychoanalysis, is to help people understand their problems through their own creations. This can be enough to overcome those problems.

The psychoanalytic approach does not involve the development of practical skills in artistic expression. This means that a person can consciously and actively understand themselves and others, make changes to themselves, and be free from being a slave to external circumstances. They can also change the environment around them instead of simply adapting to it.

Art therapy provides an opportunity to create an inner world that includes experiences, safe challenges, and problems that can be solved. The process begins with drawing, creating engravings, installing artworks, performing plays, taking photographs, or sculpting in clay. These creations are then brought into the person's everyday life.

Working with various means of artistic expression, such as color, a person can learn about their nature and methods of application. Through this process, they can find solutions to problems and gain the ability to design their own lives independently. In our country, art therapy has only recently begun to work with at-risk adolescents, people with disabilities, and victims of terrorist attacks. It started about 10–15 years ago, and programs are still being developed and projects are being proposed.

To conduct art therapy, specialists need a deeper understanding and skills in different types of artistic activities. We have created an art therapy program to help people deal with stress and its negative emotional effects. Art therapy, which involves using art or creativity, has long been considered one of the most effective ways to improve psychoemotional well-being. After all, expressing emotions, feelings, and moods is a natural part of being human, and drawing, like other creative activities, can help relieve psychoemotional stress.

Art therapy is a form of psychotherapy that utilizes the creation and analysis of artistic works. Art therapy techniques, such as drawing therapy, aim to promote self-awareness, emotional processing, and positive attitude formation through visual means. Drawing therapy is a common practice in art therapy that involves using drawing as a means of expression and communication. Through drawing, individuals can express their feelings, thoughts, and desires, as well as explore and reframe their relationships with various situations and challenging images. Drawing can also serve as a tool for understanding one's inner world and external reality, as well as for modeling relationships and conveying various emotions. Drawing has been shown to be effective in reducing mental tension, managing stress, and addressing neuroses and phobias.

Drawing is a great way to unwind and release tension, going back to more primitive forms of expression and satisfying hidden desires. It helps individuals process and deal with negative emotions, especially for those who cannot easily express themselves verbally. Drawing allows a person to project their inner thoughts and feelings onto the canvas and explore their unique perspective on the world.

Art therapy is especially helpful for children, as it helps them express their thoughts and feelings in a more creative way. It can help them deal with difficult emotions and issues and allows them to be more in touch with their inner self. It is even used with very young children, helping them develop their own unique style and personality.

Overall, drawing and art therapy are valuable tools for self-expression and self-discovery. They allow individuals to explore their inner world and find their own unique voice, while also dealing with negative emotions and finding inner harmony. Additionally, creating something independently is a great way to boost self-confidence.

The process of drawing itself teaches children to focus on their feelings, be aware of their emotions, and express them in an appropriate manner, including expressing negative emotions. Art therapy enhances children's ability to express themselves and communicate their experiences with adults. There are various approaches to art therapy, such as identifying with what is drawn, drawing without intention or following one's hand, and "collective drawing," which is particularly effective at the beginning stages of training, as it aids in team building and fostering trust. It is important to note that there are no contraindications or restrictions to this technique. Art therapy provides everyone with the opportunity to express their inner world through creative expression.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Given the significance of this issue and the potential risks associated with its consequences, it is essential that training future educators include proficiency in techniques for preventing and mitigating school-related anxiety. Art therapy has been shown to be an effective method for reducing stress and anxiety among patients in dental clinics. This technique helps enhance communication between dental professionals and patients, as well as fosters a more positive atmosphere during treatment sessions. The implementation of art therapy within the dental field can significantly improve the quality of patient care and overall satisfaction. By promoting this approach, dentists can contribute to reducing patient stress and increasing the success of treatment interventions. Awareness of emotions and coping with them often becomes a challenge for many individuals. Art therapy allows people to use creativity to recognize, experience, and express their emotions and feelings.

References:

1. Ортикова Н. Тенденция эффективности профилактических мероприятий путем коррекции психологического стресса у детей на стоматологическом приёме //Общество и инновации. 2022. Т. 3. №. 6. С. 181-189.
2. Ортикова Н. Х., Ризаев Ж. А., Мелибаев Б. А. Психологические аспекты построения стоматологического приема пациентов детского возраста //Editor coordinator. 2021. С. 554.
3. Ortikova Nargiza Xayrullayevna. The Relationship Of Dental Anxiety With Demographic Indicators.// European International Journal Of Multidisciplinary Research And Management Studies, January, 2024, Pag: 331-337
4. Ortikova Nargiza Xayrullaevna Comparison of Dental and Bone Devices with Instantaneous Expansion of the Upper Jaw in Young People. American Journal of Bioscience and Clinical Integrity, Октябрь, Vol:1, N:10 (2024), 25-29 бетлар
5. Nargiza Ortikova Influence of psycho-emotional stress on children on the state of health of the oral cavity, Жамият ва инновациялар, 07 (2023), pag:328-333
6. Axatov Alijon Jamshidovich, Ortikova Nargiza Khairullayevna Emotional And Behavioral Reactions Are A Manifestation Of Protection In Children When Visiting A Dentist // Modern education and development, Часть–3 ноябрь 2024, выпуск №14, стр 131-140
7. Ortikova Nargiza Khairullaevna, Dental Anxiety As A Special Place In Scientific Knowledge // Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal, Volume 1, Issue 29, October, 2023, pag: 104-112
8. Ortikova Nargiza Khairullaevna Features Of Children's Fear At A Dental Appointment, American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, Volume 25, February, 2024, pag: 77-82
9. Ортикова Н. Х., Ризаев Ж. А. Стоматологическая тревожность у детей перед посещением стоматолога. Тезис VI Международный конгресс стоматологов "Актуальные проблемы стоматологии и челюстно- лицевой хирургии"16 мая 2023г, стр 289-291

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2025. №11

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.